

INFLUENCE OF USER'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCES IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

By

ABDUSALAM, AHMED USMAN

Library Department Kwara State College
Of Education, Ilorin, Library.

Abstract

This study surveys the influence of users' education programme on utilization of library resources in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. The sample of the study consist of two hundred and twenty-five (225) respondents. The data was collected through the use questionnaire and the data collected were analysed using simple percentages. It was discovered that the students in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin have positive attitude towards library user education programme. Also, discovered that the programme inculcated in the respondents desired attitude towards library use habits and improved their skills in using the library. Based on this, it was recommended that the programme should be a continuous one, and adequate fund should be made available for the proper implementation of the programmes.

INTRODUCTION

As research and scholarly publications continue to proliferate the problems of accessing the information required by the library users have become substantial. Consequently, it has become imperative that users should become more skilled in order to retrieve and use resources accurately. It therefore, becomes expedient to develop an appropriate information seeking skills and behaviour among the library users especially among the students of tertiary institutions.

However, Colleges of Education in Nigeria are among the major tertiary institutions in admitting students from post primary schools that hardly even lived with books in their homes or even schools. A good number of them might never read anything outside the few prescribed textbooks. The result of this is gross deficiency in using the library for information, exploration, research and recreation. Thus, user education programme is the link between users and library resources.

User education according to Okeesan (1999) is the "various techniques of impacting the much needed knowledge". In another development, Adeoti (1998) defines user education as the primary teaching of those skills that enable students to locate and use materials in the library effectively and confidently. He further stress that since the primary aim of user education is to teach library users how best they can exploit the library both for immediate and future use, users need to be taught how to find relevant information.

Fayose (2000) posits that library resources are those materials which enable libraries to carryout their duties effectively. They are made up of books and other information bearing media Guiding user on how to make use of these library resources has become necessary because of the tremendous increase in volume of publications as well as the resulting complexity of libraries and methods by which literature is organized and disseminated. Thus, user education refers to library instruction and bibliographic instructions. The use of library is a process of making library patrons to learn how to make an effective and efficient use of the library and its resources through the acquisition of skills in identification, location, retrieval and exploitation of information (Mouglim, 1986).

Therefore, College of Education are part of what is usually referred to as the higher education or tertiary education system. They are specialized institutions established to produce professionally qualified middle level teaching workforce for the nation's pre-primary, primary and junior secondary schools. Abubakar (2003).

Literature Review

Concept of user education in libraries Pacey (1998) view the concept of user education in the United Kingdom as library by bibliographic skills taught by librarians as micro course in libraries. He stressed further that much time and money has been devoted to user education while they should be invested in practicing the concept of self explanation and re-integrating information skills.

Library user education is a means by which library users are adequately counselled in order to be able to use the resources of the library fully in the higher

institutions of learning. According to Abubakar (2003) user education is a device programme to educate the library users on how to utilize library resources effectively and stressed the importance of user education and the place of libraries in our educational institutions is not just as a store house of knowledge but where several information could be sought and got.

According to Adeyemi (2000). Users education should be a continuous process with two components i.e.

- (i) Orientations
- (ii) Bibliographic instructions

Orientations would primarily be concerned with ways of introducing the user to the general techniques of library use and services available, organizational layout, and facilitation of a particular library, while bibliographic instructions is concerned with introducing the students to the sources of information and the techniques of making use of the library resources.

Okeesan (1983) notes that the common practices of introducing students to the use of library in most higher institutions in Nigeria is via library orientation which is normally planned as part of the general orientation programmes for the new intakes. He stated further that such library orientation does not usually last more than a few days or hours featuring: -

- An address by the chief librarian, coupled with a lecture on the use of library resources.
- A guided tour of the library in groups by the fresh students to see the essential part of the library.
- Distribution of the library handbook or guide.

Objective of users Education Programme

There is the need for clearly defined objective in user education to tell them where they are going, why they want to go, and how they will get there.

Fjallbrant (1998) posits that goals and objectives of user education in an academic library must be in agreement with the general aims of the library. The aims must in turn be related to the goals and objectives of higher education. Grace (2004) describes the objectives of user education as follows:

- (i) Enable the students to explore and exploit the library resources and services more effectively.
- (ii) Inculcate into the students the desirable skills and attitudes for effective library usage.

- (iii) Create reading habit among the students because, it enables them to retrieve information of value from a library, no matter the size and complexity, with minimum delay and difficulty.
- (iv) Remove the veils of ignorance among the students who see library as a mere book store.

According to Unomah (1987), the objective of user education is that at the end of the programmes, students should be able to use their libraries in connection with their studies and future work. Lawal (2003), also spells out the objectives of user education as an instrument for helping the college library to achieve the aims and objectives of its parent institution. He stresses further that the objectives include the following:

- (a) Getting the students to develop the art of discrimination, the ability to judge the value of books in relation to his specific research needs and education as a whole.
- (b) Training independent learners, teach students to teach themselves.
- (c) Preparing the students for the continuing process of self-education (life long learning) once the formal process has been completed.

User Education and Utilization of Library Resources

The philosophy of Librarianship is based on the concept of service and the provision of a relevant materials for the user.

To this end, professional librarians continue to struggle to collect and organize printed and other items of recorded knowledge to satisfy both current and future users.

Abubakar (2003) posits that library aims at acquiring, preserving and organizing human knowledge in all forms of maximum utilization by the user while user education aims at educating an individual user towards the use of the library.

This necessitate for more user education programme in higher institutions of learning. Ahmed (1996) asserts that the main aim and objective of setting up an academic library is to acquire relevant, recent, and up to date library resources, which will be in line with the curriculum development of the parent institution. Then, to derive maximum utilization of such acquired resources is through library user education. Thus, this above assertion suggests that all efforts need to be geared towards effective utilization of the library resources and this can only be done through giving prominent attention to user education programmes.

Opaleke (1998) examined in Ajileye (1985) that the student usability level of library resources in Nigerian Universities, they reported that indexes abstracts, microfilm, library catalogue, government publications are the least used by the students. They attributed the problems to inadequate user education programmes.

Osinulu (1998) observed that students utilization of library resources are grossly under utilized because the students review classnotes instead of reading library textbooks while only few bother to consult references and audio-visual materials. Hence, there is need for library user education programme in all higher institutions of learning in Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of the study is to determine the influence of library user education on utilization of library resources. While specific objective are to:

- * Investigate the students attitude towards user education programmes
- * Assess the extent to which library user education programme has inculcated in the students desired attitude towards library use.
- * Find out to what extent the library users education programme has improved the students ability to use the library resources more effectively.
- * Examine how the programmes is been implemented.

Research Questions

The following research questions were adopted for this study:

1. What is the attitude of the student towards user educational programme in the college?
2. How far has the user education programme of the library improved the students skills in discovering information in the library?.
3. How far has the user education programme inculcated in the students the desired. attitude towards library use habit?

Methodology

The methodology adopted by the researcher is descriptive survey by using NCE 1 students to carry out the research with the help of structure questionnaire.

Research Question 1: What is the attitude of students towards user education programme in the college?

INFLUENCE OF USER'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCES IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

Table 1: Summary of responses on attitude of students towards user education programmes in the college.

S/no	Questionnaire items	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Total	%
1.	Do you attend the user education programmes frequently?	120	53.3	80	35.5	20	9.0	05	2.2	225	100
2.	Do you have positive attitude towards the user education programmes?	80	53.5	130	57.5	15	6.8	0	02	225	100
3.	Is the time allotted for the user education programme encourage you to attend the programme	125	55.6	50	22.2	30	13.3	20	8.9	225	100
4.	Is the programme well coordinated?	130	57.7	50	22.3	25	11.1	20	8.9	225	100
5.	Is the time table schedule for the programme convenient for you?	100	44.5	80	35.5	40	17.7	05	2.3	225	100

Source: Researcher's field work, 2012

Majority of the respondents attended the user education programme frequently with 88.8% of the total population agreeing, while only 11.2% disagree 93.2% of the respondent had positive attitude towards the user education programme while 68% of the respondents had negative opinion.

The time allotted for the user education programme encouraged them to attend the programmes because majority of the respondents agreed while very few had negative options.

As many as 80.0% agreed that the programme is well coordinated with the percentage scored of 80% while 20% had negative opinion. On the issue of time table schedule for the programme majority of the respondents said that the time table is very convenient for them.

Based on the findings from the analysis of research question one, it is clearly shown that students have positive attitude towards the user education in the college because, they attended the programmes promptly and frequently. The time table allotted for the programme also encourage them to attend the programme, thus the programme is well coordinated as earlier claimed by them and time scheduled is well convenient.

INFLUENCE OF USER'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCES IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

Research question 2: How far has the user education programmes inculcated in the students desired attitude towards library use habit?

Table 2: Summary of responses on how the user education programme inculcated in students desired attitudes toward library use habit

S/no	Questionnaire items	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Total	%
6.	Does user education programme influence you to visit the library regularly?	130	57.8	40	17.8	42	18.6	13	5.8	225	100
7.	Does the user education programme promote your desired attitude towards library use?	150	66.6	50	22.5	25	11.0	0	0	225	100
8.	Has the user education programme promoted your reading habit?	140	62.3	60	26.6	15	6.6	10	4.5	225	100
9.	Has the user education programmes increased the population of the students?	110	48.9	99	44.0	11	4.9	05	2.2	225	100
10.	Has your attitude to library use improved because of the programme?	125	55.6	50	22.2	40	17.7	10	4.5	225	100
11.	Has the user education programme made you more interested in using your library	134	59.6	61	27.2	10	4.4	20	8.8	225	100

Source: Research's field work 2012.

Greater proportion of the students agree that user education programme influenced them to visit the library regularly with the percentage score of 57.8%, 89.9% of the respondents indicated that the user education programme promoted their positive attitude towards library use, while 11% had negative opinion.

Similarly, 66.6% of the respondents submitted that user education programme promoted their reading habit, while 44.0% agreed that user education programme increased the population of the students towards using the library, thus showing positive impact of user education programme on utilization of library resources.

Results from the table 2 also reveals further that 55.6% of the respondents opined that user education programmes improved their library use habit. In the same vein, about 59.6% of the respondents agreed that user education programme made them more interested in using the library.

Therefore, it is clearly shown that majority of the respondents agreed with the opinion of the researcher, while very few disagree, one can conclude that the user education programme inculcated in the students the desired attitude towards library use in college of education, Ilorin.

INFLUENCE OF USER'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCES IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

Research question 3: How far has the user education programme of the library improved the students skills in discovering information in the library.

Table 3: Summary of responses on students skills in discovering and using information in the library with the aid of user education programme.

Sno	Questionnaire items	SA	%	A	%	D	%	SD	%	Total	%
12.	Has your institution user education programmes helped in facilitating your search for information resources in the library?	154	68.4	56	24.9	10	4.4	5	2.3	225	100
13.	Has the knowledge gained in user education exposed you to more information resources?	140	62.2	60	26.7	25	11.1	0	0	225	100
14.	Has the user education programme improved your ability to use card catalogue effectively to search for books in the library?	115	51.1	90	40.0	20	8.9	0	0	225	100
15.	Have you learnt to use the journal kardex through the user education programmes?	145	64.5	40	20.0	25	11.1	10	4.4	225	100
16.	Has the user education programmes assisted you to know the arrangement of the library materials?	133	57.2	77	34.2	05	2.2	10	4.4	225	100
17.	Has the user education programme assisted you in locating the materials in the library?	176	78.2	34	15.2	15	6.6	0	0	225	100

Source: Research's field work 2012

The study revealed that user education programme helped them in facilitating search for information resources in the library with the percentage score of 93.3%. This showed great impact of user education programme on the students in college of education, Ilorin.

About 88.9% of respondents opined that knowledge gained in user education programmes exposed them to more information resources. This implies that user education programme serve a s eye opener for the library users. The high proportion of the respondents agreed that user education programme improved their ability to

use the card catalogue more effectively to search for books in the library. This implied that users have acquired enough skills in using library catalogue which serve as a key to the library collections.

About 84.5% of the respondents agreed that they have learned how to use journal Kardex through user education programme, while 15.5% of the respondents disagreed.

The analysis in table 3.3 shows clearly that library user education programme assisted the users, to know the arrangement of the library materials. The research inferred that this is possible through the library tour and library practical which is part of the formal method of user education programme. In the same vein, majority of the respondents submitted that user education programme assisted them on how to locate materials in the library.

This equally inferred that they have acquired the knowledge of location skills during the user education programme.

Furthermore, majority of the respondents agreed that user education programme assisted them in knowing how to handle library materials. In this regards, based on the positive submission of the respondents, it is inferred that library user education programme improved the students skills in discovering and using information in the library.

Discussion of Result

Result of the study revealed that students in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin have positive attitude towards the user education programme. This can be seen in table 1 item (1-5), this finding corresponds with the responses of the librarians on interview conducted for them when they assert that most students are eager to listen to series of instruction on the use of the library.

Another finding in this study shows that the user education programme inculcated in students the desired attitude towards library use habits. This findings is supportive of Abubakar (2003) who argued that user education is a programme to educate library users on how to use the library resources effectively and to inculcate in them the positive attitude towards library use.

The above assertion also correspond with the responses of the librarians on interview conducted that, responses of students on library use have been encouraging particularly following orientations.

It has also been revealed in the findings that user education programme improved students' skills in discovering and using information. The finding corroborates the finding of Grace (2004) that the significance of the library in the

academic life of the students is on the degree of effective and efficient use of the library and its information resources to the maximum. Thus, the librarians have to instruct the students on how to use the library, but the librarians have divergent opinions on this, some assert that students have not shown much improvement in their skills and in using resource in spite of library education while others says that the programme improve their use of the library.

The findings also revealed that user education programme is well implemented in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin based on the responses of the College librarian and other librarians. They generally agreed that, the orientation at the orientation arena for fresh students, library orientation compulsory GST 112 course, distribution of printed guide and library practical are well coordinated in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.

This is in line with the submission of Zaki (1998) that with the increasing complexity of academic library resources, current emphasis on individual study and research and the introduction of modern communication tools, user education is the only way that provide solution for easy, effective, and efficient use of academic libraries.

Conclusion

User education programme in libraries is an essential ingredient to the effective utilization of library resource. Thus, it was found out in the library studied i.e. Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin, library that students have positive attitude towards the programme.

The importance of the library user education programme is underscored by the fact that the library studied has well designed and defined user education programme, which includes both formal and informal methods and this has been put in place since the inception of studied college library. Since the programme is well implemented in the college library, it improved the skills of their students in discovering and using information which make them to search for information with no stress. Also it exposed them to more information resources, improves their handling of more information resources, exposes them to use card catalogue, journal kardex etc more effectively. The programme has also inculcated in the students the desired attitude towards library use habit.

Finally, user education programme has positive influence on the students of Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin because the programme has broaden their horizon, equip them to use the library better and also make them to have confidence in their abilities to study independently.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from both the summary of findings and the conclusion derived from the findings as enumerated above, it becomes quite clear and important that certain useful recommendations be made as follows:

- The programme should not be a once in a while affairs rather it should be a continuous exercise and the librarians must evolve ways of sustaining it. It is wrong to assume that once the students passed the course on the use of library, they have mastered the techniques of using the library, no course on library instruction runs more than a semester as at now and so there is a need for more prolonged programme.
- Adequate fund should be made available for the proper implementation of the programme by the studied college authority, so that incentives could be given to the lecturers during orientation and acquiring of ICT materials for play back for the students.
- The orientation should be made more thorough probably in batches with the students of the studied college of education Ilorin so that small number of students would be attended to in batch for good attention.

Finally, the management of the studied college library should try to educate their library staff to be more friendly with the students and attend to them as at when due.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, A. (2003) "College of Education Libraries: The need for more emphasis on user education. Issa Kaita Multidisciplinary Journal of Education 1, 15-21.
- Adeoti, A.W.B. (1998). The impact of library instruction programme on students effective use of University Libraries Ilorin middle belt Journal of Library and information science 2. 1 & 2: 6-15.
- Adeyemi, B.M. (2000). User education programme in Nigerian University Libraries. A need of restructuring frontiers of information library science review 4: 23-31.
- Ahmed, A.O. (1996). Library User education as a vehicle towards academic excellence Oro College of Education as a case study. Journal of Arts and Social Sciences. Oro 1.1: 109-114.
- Fayose, P. (2000). Library resources and their role in education. Ibadan: the centre for external studies, University of Ibadan.
- Ajileye, A. (1985). Nigerian Library and Information Science Review. Journal of Oyo State NLA.
- Fjalbrant, N. (1984): User education in Libraries. 2nd edition London: Clive Bingley.
- Fjalbrant N (1998). The functions of the University library. Journal of Documentation 2. 5: 78-85.
- Grace, G. (2004). The effect of library instruction programme on the students' use of the library: the case of University of Abuja. A journal of Teacher Education 12:1: 51-56.
- Lawal, B.S. (2003). The importance of user education programme in Kwara State tertiary institutions. Journal of teacher education trend 1:190-196.
- Muoghin, E. (1986). User Education: "The quite essence of quality readers services for teacher education libraries in Nigeria" Nigerbiblios 4:20-26.

INFLUENCE OF USER'S EDUCATION PROGRAMMES ON UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY RESOURCES IN KWARA STATE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION, ILORIN.

Okeesan, O. (1999). Branching programme instruction as a method of instructing students in the use of the library, the College Review 1.30-40.

Opakele, J.S. (1998). Effect of the user programme on undergraduate students' library exploration at the University of Ilorin. The international information and library review. 30: 275-287.

Osinulu, L.F. (1998). Library use in Ogun State University: a survey. Gateway library 1.2:81-87.

Pacey, P. (1995). Teaching user education learning information skill towards the self explanation library. the review of academic librarianship: 1.95-103

Unomah, J.I. (1987). Student utilization of academic libraries in Nigeria: the example of two universities. Nigeria library and information science review 6. 251-257.

Zaki, O. (1998). User education in Nigeria College of Education Libraries in the 21 century Abuja: committee of Colleges of Education Librarian in Nigeria 24111 - 29th March.